

Abstract

Scalp Acupuncture for Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy: A Pilot Clinical Observation of Three Oncology Cases.

Paula Sousa^{1*}, Madalena Deus², Mariana Pedrosa², Hirondina Borges³, Alcinda Cruz³, Jorge Machado¹, and António Moreira^{4,5}.

¹ ICBAS - School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal;

² Independent researcher;

³ Oncology Department of Agostinho Neto Hospital, Cape Verde;

⁴ Polytechnic Institute of Santarém – School of Sports of Rio Maior, Portugal;

⁵ CIDESD - The Research Centre in Sports Sciences, Health Sciences and Human Development, Portugal;

* Correspondence: pasousa32@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy (CIPN) remains a prevalent and debilitating side effect associated with taxanes and platinum-based compounds, often leading to dose reduction or treatment discontinuation. This pilot observation aimed to evaluate the potential benefits of Zhu's Scalp Acupuncture (ZSA) in improving neuropathic symptoms and quality of life in oncology patients undergoing chemotherapy.

Methods: Three patients diagnosed with breast or gastrointestinal cancer and presenting with moderate to severe CIPN were selected from an oncology department. All had received taxane or platinum-based regimens. A scalp acupuncture protocol based on the ZSA methodology was designed and applied by the same practitioner, every other day over a four-week period. Clinical outcomes were assessed using the SF-36, EORTC QLQ-C30, and the CIPN20 questionnaire at baseline and post-intervention.

Results: All three patients reported marked improvement in neuropathic symptoms, including pain, numbness, and functional mobility. Quantitative analysis of the questionnaires indicated significant enhancement in physical functioning, global health status, and neuropathy-specific items. No adverse effects related to acupuncture were observed.

Conclusion: These preliminary observations suggest that ZSA may offer a promising complementary approach in the management of CIPN. Further controlled studies are warranted to validate these findings and explore their mechanisms of action.

Keywords: Oncology; Neuropathy; Chemotherapy; Scalp acupuncture.

Citation: Sousa P., Deus M, Pedrosa M., Borges H., Cruz A., Machado J., Moreira A. Scalp Acupuncture for Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy: A Pilot Clinical Observation of Three Oncology Cases. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(2) 10.5281/zenodo.16812348

Received: 19 May 2025

Accepted: 21 May 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 2nd International Congress on Complementary Therapies in Health, held on 28 June 2025.